

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HOLDER****FIRST NAME: ALISON****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 0%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE DME-ACA401D

1. What are the two main forms in which a writer can commit plagiarism?

- Using the words of others without using quotation marks and/or using ideas from a source without citing the source.¹**
- Copying text from the internet and re-arranging the words so that it is not verbatim.
- Building a concept that is close to existing theories and/or modifying a concept and claiming it as your own.
- Having someone type your work and submit it as though you typed it and making inaccurate citations.

2. Which statement BEST describes academic research?

1. Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA401/ ACA 401-D Coursepack Period, Fourth Edition* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 14.

- A process of inquiry using mixed methods to find an answer to a problem.
- A field of study that purely examines the existing theories and models with the aim of proving, disproving, or improving the area of study.
- The branch of research undertaken by academics for scholastic purposes.
- The systematic inquiry to answer a question that the researcher and others seek a solution.** ²

3. Why is it important to “question your topic”?

- It helps the researcher to be more confident about the topic.
- It focuses the researcher’s efforts by narrowing the information gathered to just those that answer the questions related to the topic’s relevance to the larger context.** ³
- It shows the reason for choosing the topic.
- It is a requirement of academic writing.

4. Which of the following describes the components of dissertation research documents?

- Concept Paper, Dissertation, Manuscript
- Dissertation Concept Paper and Dissertation.
- Dissertation Concept Paper, Dissertation Prospectus, Dissertation, and Dissertation Manuscript.** ⁴

2. Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition: Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19.

3. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 26.

4. James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

- Dissertation and Manuscript.
5. This aspect of the methodology can be stated in null or directional format.
- Problem statement.
- Research result.
- Hypothesis.**⁵
- Research question.
6. Bias occurs when the researcher believes in the relationship between variables irrespective of the findings or when the need to advocate for action influences the conclusions drawn from the findings. Which of the following is NOT a source of research bias?
- Population.
- Stereotypes.**⁶
- Intervention.
- Experience.
7. Which of the following BEST describes the goal of procedures prior to, during and after data collection?
- A detailed description of the resources and sequential actions taken to collect the data that is to be analyzed.**⁷
- A checklist of activities to be done when collecting research data.

5. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 35.

6. Sampson, 8-9.

7. Sampson, 50-53.

- A description of the research methodology.
 - A guide on how to conduct research.
8. Which of the following writing styles is described as a linguistics convention that is based on British and Irish English?
- The Turabian Guide.
 - The APA.
 - The Chicago Style.
 - The European Commission English Guide.⁸**
9. What is the main purpose of measures in the research methodology?
- To measure the correctness of variables.
 - To assess the performance of variables that are included in research questions and variables.⁹**
 - To test hypotheses.
 - To prove the research is sound.
10. “Provides evidence that the total content or factor-derived scale of scores of the measure is associated with other measures of similar constructs in a theoretically consistent direction.” What does the preceding statement describe?
- Convergent Validity.¹⁰**

8. European Commission, *English Style Guide*, 2021, 4.

9. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 37.

10. *Ibid.*, 41.

Factorial Validity.

Criterion Validity.

Factorial Validity.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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